

NET-Fuels deliverable report

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

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Methodologies for the sustainability analysis of the NET-Fuels technology

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NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
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FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (LEITAT)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

Table of Contents

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1.1 TASK 4.1 DESCRIPTION	5
1.2 JOINT WORK SESSIONS	6
2 GENERAL GOAL STATEMENT AND SYSTEM BOUNDARIES.....	7
2.1 PRODUCT SYSTEM	7
2.1.1 <i>NET-Fuels' product system pathway towards Impact.....</i>	<i>8</i>
2.1.2 <i>Target beneficiaries of the results.....</i>	<i>11</i>
2.1.3 <i>Effects of the European Council decision on e-fuels on the definition of system boundaries, processes and wording.....</i>	<i>12</i>
2.1.4 <i>System boundaries addition to account for social acceptance.....</i>	<i>14</i>
3 REFERENCE PRODUCT SYSTEM AND SCENARIOS	16
3.1 REFERENCE PRODUCT SYSTEMS.....	16
3.2 SCENARIOS	16
4 FUNCTIONAL UNITS, IMPACT CATEGORIES AND CHARACTERIZATION MODELS, TIME HORIZON	18
4.1 FUNCTIONAL UNITS	18
4.2 IMPACT CATEGORIES AND CHARACTERIZATION MODELS	19
4.3 TIME HORIZON	21
5 DATA FLOW, DATA SOURCES, AND DATA SHARING	22
6 CONCLUSIONS	23
7 REFERENCES (IF REQUIRED).....	24

List of abbreviations

List of abbreviations	
EBC	European Biochar Certificate
ESAB	Exploitation, Stakeholders and Advisory Board
FU	Functional Unit
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Green House Gases
ILCD	Reference Life Cycle Data System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NGO	Nongovernmental Organization
PR	Project Result
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small And Medium-Sized Enterprises
STES	Socio-Technical-Ecological System
syCH ₄	Synthetic Methane
Tbd	To Be Defined
TCR	Thermo-Catalytic Reforming
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report summarizes the work developed under NET-Fuels WP4 (Sustainability and carbon sink assessment) Task 4.1 (Ensure reproducibility, transparency, and comparability of the sustainability assessment) in the period 01/11/2022 to 31/10/2023. Task 4.1 involves the creation of a common ground among the partners and a framework for sustainability assessments. In order to coordinate planned activities and foster communication and discussion among partners on preliminary and critical decisions, a document was created and shared among all partners. The document (which all partners had access to and could edit) served to have a shared virtual place where questions and concerns could be asked and answered. Along with the document, working sessions were held with all or part of the partners to work on specific issues.

The insights from the meetings, and the information shared and discussed in the shared document, are organized and summarized in this document. The task goal is to create a common knowledge base on which to build the next steps of the project. One among the objectives is to anticipate and answer questions and resolve any doubts that may later be obstacles to the progress of the planned activities.

In this document, a description of the framework for sustainability assessments is presented, including system boundaries, reference biofuel production systems, time horizon of the analysis, preliminary definition of the functional units, preliminary identification and selection of scenarios, preliminary decision about impact categories.

A summary of the main decisions is given in the following:

- NET-Fuels product system includes the exploitation of farm/forestry biomass and residual biomass, and generation of synthetic methane, oxygen, TCR crude bio-oil, hydrogen, biochar (with subsequent generation of immaterial carbon credits)
- Target audiences include large industrial stakeholders and SMEs, the research community, and policy makers
- An ethnographic study of the NET-Fuels project and stakeholders mapping is to be integrated to the perspective system dynamic model
- Different time horizons will be used in the study, to have a prediction of the effects of the introduction of NET-Fuels technology but maintaining a certain degree of confidence in the data.
- It was decided to use a product-oriented approach, and commensurate everything with the production of a given amount of synthetic methane.
- Different scenarios and product system variations have been identified, and they are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 - Scenarios and reference system variations

Scenarios and reference system variations					
APPROACH ¹	FEEDSTOCK	FUNCTIONAL UNIT	BASELINE	ALTERNATIVES	REFERENCE SYSTEM
Product oriented	prunings	MJ of energy	production of syCH ₄ , H ₂ , O ₂ , TCR crude bio-oil, biochar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TCR crude bio-oil is burnt • the bio crude oil is sent to the refinery and with H₂ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • same products produced from fossil sources • same products produced from renewable sources
	Calamity wood				
	Digestate				
Process oriented	prunings	tonnes of wood with 20% moisture content			
	Calamity wood	tonnes of wood with 20% moisture content			
	Digestate	m ³ of digestate			

1.1 Task 4.1 description

Task 4.1 aims at providing a common ground (methods, uniformity of intentions, audience) and framework for sustainability assessments also regarding WP5 and WP6. UNIBO, SUT and ITHAKA will organise 3-6 joint work sessions to plan and realise the following:

- system boundaries from the collection of the feedstock (gate) to the end use of the NET-Fuels technology products (gate/wheel/farm) and geographical extent;
- reference biofuel production systems for the comparison with NET-Fuels performances;
- time horizon of the analysis with reference to the time scale for carbon sink;
- preliminary definition of the functional units (e.g., process or product oriented);
- preliminary identification and selection of scenarios and product-system variations regarding feedstocks and number of impact categories;

¹ Definitions are included within the document.

- f) preliminary decision about impact categories and characterization models in preparation for Task 4.2;
- g) data flow, data sources and data sharing between the tasks in WP4, planning of the use of primary data (from NET-Fuels pilot plant) and use of secondary data (generic data from literature or scientific papers or average data from LCA databases, industry association reports, government statistics, etc).

Choices impacting communication and exploitation will be flagged as critical. Preliminary decisions and critical choices will be discussed within the Management Board to make sure that the model choices are functional to NET-Fuels objectives.

1.2 Joint work sessions

To make the decisions to refine the framework of the project, several methods were used. This document is an aggregation of views and opinions provided by the entire consortium. Meetings (in-person and virtual) were held to create it, and a shared document was created where all partners could enter questions and input to reason about and for other colleagues to respond to, so that there would be an ongoing conversation over time.

Table 2 - Work session

Work session			
	Date	Involved partners	Notes
Consortium meeting @Sulzbach-Rosenberg	18-19/04/2023	All	Illustration and explanation of the document; new European fuel law;
On-line	29/05/2023	SUT/ITHAKA	LCA parameter evaluation; time horizon, functional units. (ITHAKA was unable to attend)
On-line	26/06/2023	SUT	New member introduction, document explanation, progress in choosing and evaluating LCA parameters, software evaluation to be used
On-line interaction	01/06 - 17/10/2023	All	Discussions and contributions on preliminary versions of the D4.1 deliverable (shared online)

2 General goal statement and system boundaries

In WP4 we perform a sustainability assessment thus addressing multiple dimensions such as environment, economy, social acceptance, standardization, and certification of negative emissions as well as carbon (C) sinks. In Task 4.1, the aim is to describe the approach for accomplishing the assessment across different dimensions. The first step is to understand what the scope of our analysis is. The second step is to better understand what the scope is and with reference to existing practices and norms, by stating:

- The intended application of the sustainability analysis
- The reasons for carrying out such assessment
- The intended audience, i.e., to whom the results of the study are intended to be communicated
- Whether the results are intended to be used in comparative assertions and
- If results are intended to be disclosed to the public.

Therefore, it is essential for us to understand and recognize the needs and roles of stakeholders related to our life cycle study to appropriately determine the goal and subsequent scope of the assessment. We can formulate that as the following list of questions:

What is the product system?

What is the intended application of the sustainability assessment, i.e., what are the reasons for carrying out the study?

What is the impact of our product system to interested parties and stakeholders?

To whom the results of the study are intended to be communicated?

Are we using the results in comparative assertions?

What are the system boundaries through WP4?

2.1 Product system

A product system is a collection of unit processes with elementary (Selin & Selin, 2023) and product flows (Petry et al., 2020), performing one or more defined functions, and which models the life cycle of a product. The system boundary, then, defines which processes will be included in, or excluded from, the scope of the analysis. In general, it is helpful to describe the system using a process flow diagram showing the processes and their relationships (ISO 14040).

Figure 1 represents the NET-Fuels product system in LCA terms. On the left we see the farm systems (F) providing feedstock. This is densified/dried at intermediary stations in the supply chain, ready to be treated in our production system: this is the farm gate (G) to the process. In the middle, the technological installation which will generate at the factory gate (G) the following products a) synthetic methane (European Commission, 2021; JRC., 2012) (e-fuel), b) (green) oxygen c) TCR crude bio-oil and (green/ low carbon hydrogen) hydrogen (Ahlborg et al., 2019), d) biochar. It must be noted that the latter is returned to the farm systems; the biochar is “processed” through a certification system and will generate an intangible product in the form of carbon credits. If used for mobility purposes the system shall include a refinery and methane distribution grids to the final use at the “wheel” (W).

Then, the product system can be defined as the following:

- 1) adding value to farm/forestry biomass and residual biomass
- 2) generating:

- a) Synthetic methane
- b) Oxygen
- c) TCR crude bio-oil
- d) Hydrogen
- e) Biochar (and subsequently production of immaterial carbon credits*)

The purpose of the system is:

- to use disposed secondary biomass
- generating chemical products and biochar
- generating carbon storage

Figure 1 – NET-Fuels product system in LCA terms

* Carbon credits: There are several terms to express the act of removing/sinking carbon: carbon credits, carbon removal certificates, carbon sink certificates. Each of these words implies different acceptations: “carbon credit” is a general term referring to the buying and selling of emissions permits or carbon credits that can be either distributed by a regulatory body or generated through carbon storage projects. This term includes emission avoidance certificates and other “low grade” products and thus should not be used within the context of NET-fuels.² “Carbon sink” or C-sink certificate is EBC language and indicates the certification of (1) removal of carbon (CO₂) from the atmosphere, (2) transformation of the carbon into a stable form that can be stored, and (3) verifiable, long-term carbon storage, e.g., in the soil or in materials (carbon capture, transformation and storage). Carbon removal certificate calls into question the European Commission proposal for a first EU-wide voluntary framework to reliably certify high-quality carbon removals (Nov. 2022).

2.1.1 NET-Fuels’ product system pathway towards Impact

To address the impact of the NET-Fuels system in specific value chains, we have to consider the project results (products and/or processes from the project), as well as the materials used / needed (feedstock, etc), and to precisely identify the stakeholders (as started in GA. Page 24). Table 3 schematically summarizes the target audiences of the project.

Table 3 – NET-Fuels target audiences

NET-Fuels target audiences

² <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2023/jan/18/revealed-forest-carbon-offsets-biggest-provider-worthless-verra-aoe>

Large industrial stakeholders and SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Technology suppliers •Engineering companies •Fuel distributors and supplier •Vehicle manufacturers •Agricultural industry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Livestock farmers Forest industry Process food industry Winery/fruit farmers •Petrol-chemical industries •Biofuel distribution companies •Waste management companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Deploying the technology themselves or → Integrating it within their value chains → Find a new valorisation pathway for their residues or for the use of biochar → Making use of the net-fuels outputs
Research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Research organizations and institutes •Individuals spanning related fields such as biofuels research, clean energy research, environmental sciences 	This organizations will benefit from new data produced and/or collected within the NET-Fuels project, using them for the development and advance of research
Prosumers	•Renewable energy cooperatives	Integrate with the net-fuels system
Policy makers and legislature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •European commission, European parliament •National authorities •Regional and local authorities 	Guidelines to support legislative frameworks related to the results of the research activities
NGOs and charities	•Environmental organizations	Tbd
General public	Tbd	Tbd

Specifically, the following aspects should be considered.

- 1. Identification of the specific stakeholders that will benefit directly or indirectly from the expected results of the project, and that will be interested on all or on some of the specific materials, processes and project results. Classify those stakeholders with respect to suitable use-case scenarios and respective exploitation pathways (e.g.: see table below).**

Below, in Table 4 some possible use-cases for exploitation pathways related to the project’s materials and resulting products can be found:

Table 4 - NET-Fuels exploitation pathways

NET-Fuels exploitation pathways		
NET-Fuels	Stakeholders /	Potential

Materials /Products	Potential End-Users	Exploitation Pathway
Feedstock Supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Livestock farmers • Forest industry • Process food industry • Waste management companies 	→ A new valorisation pathway for their residues
TCR crude bio-oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Petro-Chemical industries; Biofuel distribution companies; Automotive Industry • Marine Industry 	→ Production of biofuel (+HDO and distillation) for vehicles → Use as a marine fuel
Biochar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers in general • Cement industry • C-sink certification companies 	→ Soil amendment → Cement quality enhancement → Carbon credit
Hydrogen - H2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrogen automotive industry • TCR crude bio-oil upgrade 	→ Hydrogen as a fuel for vehicles → Refinery crude oil into EN-compliant biofuels – gasoline and diesel (To-SYN-Fuel)
Synthetic Methane	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Sector • Transportation Sector • Petrochemical industry • Agriculture 	→ Light, power and heat for homes and businesses/ Turbines → Used as a fuel for vehicles → Production of methanol, hydrogen cyanide and acetylene → Production of fertilizer ³

To evaluate the impact that the project exploitation will imply on them, the work that will support this evaluation includes the work being carried out in WP4 (T4.1) of sustainability assessment with the definition of suitable application scenarios, together with the results from the technology research and market analysis of WP5, and the exploitation strategy and activities designed for NET-Fuels on WP6 (T6.4).

³ <https://www.yara.com/crop-nutrition/crop-and-agronomy-knowledge/how-we-make-our-fertilizer/>

2. **Identification of Use-Cases for potential application scenarios, considering all the main project results (PRs) of the project solution (Biochar; TCR crude bio-oil; H₂; Synthetic Methane, etc.), available to feed market value-chains jointly or in separate scenarios.**

For assessing the valorisation of the exploitable results, it is also necessary that we consider the application scenarios that the project solution and results will be employed. The impact will be mostly dependent on the type of use cases we consider.

3. **Analysis of the applied solution to some specific selected value-chains and use-cases' scenarios, which reflect the use of all main PRs, including:**
 - a. Identification of the impact indicators to each scenario. For example: Bioenergy carriers conversion parameters; Sustainable levels of feedstock and of Biofuel production; Levels of the biomass conversion efficiency; Technology improvements; PRs quality and usage; Environmental impact indicators; cost-benefit assessment; etc.
 - b. Evaluation of the direct benefits, outcomes and impacts of the project via the efforts from WP4, WP5 and WP6.
4. **Overall contribution of the project results and development processes to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)⁴, including impact identification for SDG 7; SDG 8; SDG 9; SDG 10; SDG 12; SDG 13; and SDG 15, indifferent aspects and intensities.**
 - a. SDG 7 - Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.
 - b. SDG 8 - Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
 - c. SDG 9 - Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
 - d. SDG 10 - Reduce inequality within and among countries.
 - e. SDG 12 - Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
 - f. SDG 13 - Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
 - g. SDG 15 - Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
5. **Overall contribution of the project achievements in relation to the EU Taxonomy Regulation Environmental Objectives⁵ (as proposed in GA Page 15), the six environmental objectives of the Taxonomy being:**
 - (1) climate change mitigation,
 - (2) climate change adaptation,
 - (3) sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources,
 - (4) transition to a circular economy,
 - (5) pollution prevention and control,
 - (6) protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems

2.1.2 Target beneficiaries of the results

We might decide to use the results only internally or externally or in a mixed way. Our study can be useful

⁴ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁵ <https://www.spglobal.com/esg/insights/a-short-guide-to-the-eu-s-taxonomy-regulation>

for different stakeholders, certain interests, needs and responsibilities. There are different ‘planets’ of industrial and academic users, each with a different background but believing to talk about the same (Klöpffer & Heinrich, 2001). We should be clear from the beginning about our methods, approach and how the study should be used. The process of developing our assessment shall be open and transparent and shall include consultation with relevant stakeholders’ parties. Reasonable efforts should be made to achieve a consensus throughout the process (adapted from ISO 14020:2000, 4.9.1, Principle 8).

The review should ensure the quality of the study as follows:

- methods are consistent with (ISO) standards wherever appropriate,
- data are appropriate and reasonable in relation to the goal of the study,
- limitations are set and explained,
- assumptions are explained,
- report is transparent and consistent, and the type and style are oriented to the intended audience.

The results are intended to be communicated within:

- the consortium,
- to the Exploitation, Stakeholders and Advisory Board (ESAB),
- to the commissioning European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA),
- to the public at large.

2.1.3 Effects of the European Council decision on e-fuels on the definition of system boundaries, processes and wording

On March 28th, 2023, the Council adopted a regulation that sets the standard for new cars and vans in terms of CO₂ emissions that will decide the fate of alternative fuels. From 2023 to 2034, new cars on the market should produce half the emissions compared to 2021, while from 2035 the level is set at zero emissions.

The regulation followed a heated debate at the EU level and the deal has included, after pressure from the German government, a reference regarding the possibility to exclude synthetic fuels, such as e-fuels, that run combustion-engine cars, since they could be climate neutral soon. The regulation does not specifically mention e-fuels but does make a reference to CO₂-neutral fuels because of the above-mentioned reason. However, the agreed-on deal **does not envisage this possibility for biofuels**.

Apart from the negotiations between member states and supranational institutions, it is important to give a clear definition of the two alternative fuels and how they impact the market. First, the production of **e-fuel relies on extracting hydrogen through an electrolysis process** that involves breaking down water into its constituent elements of hydrogen and oxygen. Electricity is necessary to power this process as well as other subsequent production stages. Therefore, to generate a liquid energy carrier, hydrogen is combined with CO₂ obtained from the atmosphere.

Instead, **biofuels originate from biomass energy**. The latter encompasses a range of sources, including biogas, liquid biofuels (such as biodiesel, ethanol, methanol and butanol), and solid biofuels (typically wood, although any solid substance that can generate heat through combustion can be used). Solid biofuels can be directly burnt to produce energy, while biogas and liquid biofuels require conversion processes before they can be used as fuel. There are multiple methods for converting biomass into fuels that can power homes, vehicles and other energy needs. The specific conversion process depends on the type of biomass (e.g., manure or oilseed crops) and its intended use (e.g., fuel for cars or generators). This clearly calls into cause NET-Fuels because of the TCR crude bio-oil flow. Results have been obtained putting together preliminary data included in the proposal (GA pp. 12-13 Part B) and deliverable D6.3 of the To-Syn-Fuel project. Three scenarios were considered:

1) The first is the refinery route Figure 2 : TCR crude bio-oil - which has proven conversion route (at TRL7) and

can make use of the additional H₂ produced in the proposed plant. By doing so, the aim of the system is to increase the biomass conversion efficiency up to 35-40%.

Figure 2 - refinery route

2) The second option (Figure 3) consider TCR crude bio-oil as an isolated energy carrier. It can be used to generate heat & power to meet local process needs. That would reduce the conversion efficiency however it will increase the energy balance and will make H₂ flow as an additional product to be exported out of the factory gate.

Figure 3 – Heat & Power route

3) A third option (Figure 4) is for TCR crude bio-oil to be intended for marine-type engines. In this way, TCR crude bio-oil would not require refining and could be used for power generation.

Figure 4 - marine-type engines route

The three different options also differ in their efficiency (biomass conversion efficiency) (η) and carbon negativity (c-negativity). This information is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Efficiency and c-negativity of the three different routes of TCR crude bio-oil.

2.1.4 System boundaries addition to account for social acceptance

Employing the socio-technical-ecological system (STES) approach developed by Ahlborg et al., 2019, our analysis reframes the understanding of technology as exogenous to society and the environment. Instead, we regard “society, technology, and environment as co-constituted and co-emergent entities” (Ahlborg et al., 2019), with technology being at the interface of the human-environment relationship and the principal mediator between nested, complex and adaptive social and ecological systems. From this standpoint, the NET-Fuels technology shall be understood both as *emerging from* and *embedded into* a particular socio-ecological system, as well as an attempt to *mediate* between society and its environment in an innovative way, one that is beneficial to both, and is circular and regenerative rather than linear and extractive. As such, it provides an alternative and a challenge to the current energy system/regime, potentially reshaping its human-environment relationship and power relations.

Viewing technology as the principal mediator in the human-environment relationship requires the study of how technological change impacts social and ecological systems, as well as how these in turn determine the adoption, implementation, and outcomes of technological change. For instance, assessing and communicating the potential co-benefits of technology, for both society and ecosystems, may improve its social acceptance and thus also reduce the political capital necessary for policy change in its favor. On the contrary, failing to consider relevant, yet hardly quantifiable non-technical factors bear the risk of underestimating their impact on the project and its outcomes (Freeman 2021). As biochar is a direct product of NET-Fuels, we suggest the assessment of its co-benefits should be given priority. Yet, also others, relatively indirect ones could be assessed, such as the improvements for human and crop health from the reduction of atmospheric pollution and GHG, and the strengthening of energy security through the production of energy and biofuels from secondary biomass.

The proposed system boundaries expansion could be achieved, on one hand, by assessing the co-benefits of the NET-Fuels technology through the LCA and communicating them to the stakeholders; and, on the other, by “modelling the socio-political feasibility of the project with system dynamics” (Freeman 2021). As a frame of reference, we suggest Freeman’s TEMPEST model, which allows for the integration of (quantifiable) technical and (hardly quantifiable) societal factors into a system dynamic model (Freeman, 2021). In this regard, we tentatively propose a few topics of research that could be critical for the project implementation: the potential impact of cost factors (e.g., the cost of biochar and for providing the secondary biomass) and cultural factors (e.g., value given to healthy soils, renting Vs. owning land) on the participation of farmers; the current policy framework and incentives/subsidies Vs. fiscal structure regarding biofuels; and, the effect of increasing levels of land and water resources pollution, also due to extreme weather events (e.g., the May 2023 flood in Emilia-Romagna region), on the economic valuation and social acceptance of biochar.

For the assessment and integration of all relevant non-technical factors, we propose to conduct an ethnographic study of the NET-Fuels project, mapping all the stakeholders and their connections spanning between the rural landscapes and this cutting-edge industrial technology. Multi-sited ethnography indeed allows to “follow the thing” both “upstream and downstream” from the site of production or utilization/consumption, allowing the discovery of its “global relations with social and environmental impacts” (Cederlöf & Hornborg, 2021). Therefore, employing ethnographic methods (e.g., focus groups, semi-structured interviews, surveys, etc.) best-suited for the different types of stakeholders (e.g., farmers, policymakers, citizens, etc.), we propose to integrate critical societal and technical factors into a system dynamic model and assist the project in its design, implementation, and dissemination.

3 Reference product system and scenarios

3.1 Reference product systems

A reference production system is needed because we contemplate to compare Net-Fuels synthetic methane production against the counterfactual use of the solid wood-based feedstock and of the liquid digestate.

When considering a process-oriented approach to sustainability analysis, the reference system in the case of calamity wood and/or fruit tree pruning is their use in CHP plants. The underlying question is: what is the environmental footprint of disposing of 1 tonne of calamity wood and/or fruit tree pruning in a CHP process in terms of NET-Fuels?

In the case of digestate, the question is: what is the environmental footprint associated with the disposal of 1 tonne of digestate when applied to land and what is the environmental footprint associated with the processing of 1 tonne of digestate in NET-Fuels?

If instead a product-oriented approach is considered, the relevant questions would be: what is the environmental footprint associated with producing 1 MJ of (thermal) energy from calamity wood and/or fruit tree pruning, compared to 1 MJ of the equivalent chemical energy contained in NET-Fuels products?

In the case of digestate, no energy is consumed, and it is used to fertilise the soil, which can be measured in kg of nitrogen (N) equivalents. N-equivalents avoid direct N₂O emissions and emissions associated with fertiliser production and can be measured as tonnes of CO_{2eq} avoided. This leads to the question: what is the carbon footprint associated with 1 tonne of avoided CO_{2eq} from the use of digestate versus 1 tonne of CO₂ removed?

Table 5 provides a synthetic overview of the problem.

Table 5 - Reference product systems

Reference product systems		
Feedstock	Process	Reference product
Calamity wood / pruning	CHP (bioenergy)	Heat and power
Digestate	Land spreading of digestate	Carbon removal

What is the best analysis approach to use within a project? There are two options: to use the process approach or the product approach. We must choose which one is best to do the evaluations and comparisons with reference systems. If we decide to use a process approach, we must decide whether to compare the NET-Fuels process to traditional energy production processes (those that use fossil fuels, for example) or to newer, more "green" processes (these processes have not yet been identified, an example might be TO-SYN-FUEL).

We propose using a product-oriented approach and commensurate everything with the production of a given amount of synthetic methane. SUT propose to use e.g., 1 t of biomass as FU, describe the process conversion up until the products, and then to recalculate the inputs/outputs per 1 MJ of methane. Allocation of environmental impacts will be based on physical properties of the products.

3.2 Scenarios

Different types of feedstocks are identified in the NET-Fuels project to feed the system. These are: pruning clippings from agriculture, calamity wood (plant biomass from extreme events), and digestate. Each of these materials is currently managed or used in some way. Some of these methods are listed in Table 6, thus constituting the alternative scenarios for the project.

Table 6 - Feedstock alternative scenarios

Scenarios

Pruning	pruning clippings produced by small farmers in Italy (how is it abroad?) are often burnt in the field
	examples of circular economy where the clippings are recovered and burnt again for energy production or used for compost production
Calamity wood	recovered and used/sold for use as firewood
	Recovered and used for energy production
	if in small quantities, is recovered and disposed of
Digestate	disposed of by incineration alone or together with municipal waste
	disposed of in landfills for special waste
	re-used in agriculture, either as such or after composting

4 Functional units, impact categories and characterization models, time horizon

4.1 Functional units

There are three system functions identified: to use disposed secondary biomass, generating chemical products and biochar, generating carbon storage. Are they one alternative to the other or should they all be considered simultaneously? As more system functions are identified, it is difficult to choose the best functional unit. If one chooses to consider them all together one must consider having multiple functional units or identify one that somehow represents all functions. Two directions have been proposed:

- the first alternative is to have a functional unit for each function of the proposed system
- the second alternative is to choose one function and consider only that function, with its single functional unit

Which functional unit (FU) best represents the "generation of chemicals and biochar" function? In a review from 2020, the problem of defining the functional unit for an LCA study on biochar production is addressed (Puettmann et al., 2020). Some proposals are discussed in the following excerpt from one of the paragraphs:

- “The functional unit, **CO₂ eq. per oven dry tonne of biochar product** was best for comparing different biochar systems. [...] a starting estimate for the climate mitigation potential of a biochar system was equal to **one metric ton of CO₂ eq. per oven dry ton of biomass.**”
- “Lee et al. (2010) examined many alternative fates for a unit of biomass in different energy and soil amendment uses. Based on air emissions and soil application impacts, they found that a biochar energy system produced less GHG emissions than composting, combustion for energy, or conversion to cellulosic ethanol.”

Another consideration is made in the study of (Matuščík et al., 2022):

- “the obvious functional unit [...] is the mass of produced biochar, **one metric tonne of biochar**. Nevertheless, the system serves other functions as well. The combined heat and power plant (CHP) unit produces electricity and heat, and the entire system is a waste treatment. *Three additional functional units were designed* to evaluate if a change in perspective can affect the conclusions: 1 MWh of electricity sold to grid (the electricity used for internal consumption is not included); 1 MWh of sold heat; and 1 metric tonne of waste pallets processed. These alternative functional units are especially important for a robust comparison with alternative systems for energy production or waste management.”

If the function of the system is to generate carbon credits, how do we identify a FU? Is there a relationship between tonnes of biochar and the number of carbon credits? Or is there a relationship between CO_{2eq} and carbon credits? We will measure the carbon storage in any case by how much carbon will be stored in the soil over a certain time (1000 years).

Table 7 - Function Units related to Process & Product oriented systems

Function Units related to Process & Product oriented systems	
	Proposed FU (Functional Unit)
process oriented	Disposal of 1 tonne of secondary biomass (dry or wet?) With 100% efficiency.
	Disposal of 1 tonne of dry wood (dry or wet?) With 100% efficiency
	Disposal of 1 m ³ of digestate (dry or wet?) With 100% efficiency
product oriented	MJ energy

	Production of 1 tonne of biochar with a lifetime of 100 years
	Production of 1 tonne of chemicals

4.2 Impact categories and characterization models

It was suggested to use in Task4.2 the impact categories and respective methods given in the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) handbook. These categories, along with the recommended methods, indicators and their classification are given in Table 8. In Task4.x, where the consequential LCA will be performed, only the impact category "Climate change" will be used, and indicators related to the identified FU.

Table 8 - Impact categories

Impact categories			
Impact category	Recommended default LCIA method	Indicator	Classification
Climate change	Baseline model of 100 years of the IPCC	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	I
Ozone depletion	Steady-state ODPs 1999 as in WMO assessment	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	I
Human toxicity, cancer effects	USEtox model (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	II/III
Human toxicity, noncancer effects	USEtox model (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTUh)	II/III
Particulate matter/Respiratory inorganics	RiskPoll model (Rabl and Spadaro, 2004) and Greco et al 2007	Intake fraction for fine particles (kg PM2.5-eq/kg)	I
Ionising radiation, human health	Human health effect model as developed by Dreicer et al. 1995 (Frischknecht et al, 2000)	Human exposure efficiency relative to U235	II
Ionising radiation, ecosystems	No methods recommended		Interim
Photochemical ozone formation	LOTOS-EUROS (Van Zelm et al, 2008) as applied in ReCiPe	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	II
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	II
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	II

	(Seppälä et al. 2006, Posch et al, 2008)		
Eutrophication, aquatic	EUTREND model (Struijs et al, 2009b) as implemented in ReCiPe	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P) or marine end compartment (N)	II
Ecotoxicity (freshwater)	USEtox model, (Rosenbaum et al, 2008)	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTUe)	II/III
Ecotoxicity (terrestrial and marine)	No methods recommended		
Land use	Model based on Soil Organic Matter (SOM) (Milà i Canals et al, 2007b)	Soil Organic Matter	III
Resource depletion, water	Model for water consumption as in Swiss Ecoscarcity (Frischknecht et al, 2008)	Water use related to local scarcity of water	III
Resource depletion, mineral, fossil and renewable	CML 2002 (Guinée et al., 2002)	Scarcity	II

4.3 Time horizon

Within the NET-Fuels project, the choice of time horizon is an important factor, as it can/must be included in several tasks of WP4, and in each one it can be extended.

In Task 4.2, SUT will perform an attributional LCA. The time horizon has long been overlooked in LCA studies, even though the point in time at which a climate-relevant emission is released is critical. The only impact factor in which time can be considered is climate change. It would be appropriate to conduct LCA with two different time horizons, for example, one at 100 years and one at 500 years.

To address the time horizon, the SUT team has been using the ReCiPe method for the impact assessment. In ReCiPe the characterization factors are categorized in terms of their time perspective (individualist, hierarchist and egalitarian).

In task 4.3 “the goal is to study in detail the effects of the NET-Fuels technology (especially GHG emissions) considering relevant conditions (parameters) of the feedstock, operations and case studies in time and localization, taking into account the future changes in the production of energy and the sustainability policies implemented in the E.U.” The time horizon thus becomes a critical parameter in Task 4.3. In fact, UNIBO will be required to conduct research into the effects of NET-Fuels technology. We will make sure that the energy mix changes, we will make different conditions change. we do this in accordance with the IEA forecast that goes up to 30 years maximum (2050/2055).

Finally, the time horizon also plays a key role in task 4.6. Here ITHAKA will develop a methodology to certify the negative emissions generated by NET-Fuels. Since these negative emissions result from the application of biochar as a carbon sink in the soil, the time horizon may vary between tens and thousands of years, depending on the characteristics of the biochar itself. Ithaka will make two predictions, one for the labile fraction and one for the permanent fraction of carbon in the soil.

5 Data flow, data sources, and data sharing

We need to understand whether the data we need already exists, whether they have already been modelled and whether they are available. It is unrealistic to think that we can only use primary data. One must therefore understand whether it is possible to obtain (whether free of charge or not) secondary data.⁶

Should we opt for primary data, we must ensure that these are generalizable and representative.

The work being developed in WP5 (Business Development and Potential Industrial Scale-up) Task T5.1 (Market and Competitive Research) about technology research and market analysis (to be concluded in month M24 of the project) can also contribute to this decision, in the sense that potential LCA data from the selected projects (related to the work in NET-Fuels) could be used for comparison as existing work.

This has an influence on the type of data that can be used: GLAD offers both national, European, and global datasets. These are secondary and generic data.

To meet the demands of the European Union that at least part of the data be made public, we may make (part of) the data from the LCA accessible via the GLAD - Global LCA data access site (<https://www.globalcadataaccess.org/>). As specified on their website, "GLAD does not directly host databases. Its main purpose is to help users find the LCA data they need. Once the user finds the data fit for their purpose, GLAD redirects them to the data provider website, from which the datasets can be downloaded, for free, or against a commercial license fee - depending on your model. The conditions under which you hand over the actual data to the individual users remains at

your sole discretion."

⁶ Also known as "foreground system" data, primary data is directly collected or measured from main sources, such as specific facilities, processes, or suppliers. Referred to as the "background system" in LCA, secondary data is already existing scientific data collected by previous researchers. It is not directly collected, measured, or estimated, but rather sourced from third-party life-cycle-inventory databases. Secondary data provides (average) environmental background data on supply chains, filling the gaps when companies don't have access to all their primary data.

6 Conclusions

An initial framework of the NET-Fuels project is proposed in this paper. Several options were evaluated regarding the system boundaries of the project, the time horizon considered, and the fate of different products generated in the project (TCR crude bio-oil, hydrogen, oxygen and methane. Decisions were made regarding the terminology used within the project and in dissemination activities.

All partners were made participants in the discussions that led to the preparation of this document. Some parts may be further elaborated after the referenced Work Packages begin.

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